

**SPORTSPERSONSHIP, SELF-EFFICACY AND SPORTS MOTIVATION
OF SOCCERSARGEN REGIONAL ATHLETIC
ASSOCIATION (SRAA) ATHLETES**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 1

Pages: 178-188

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2045

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12747459

Manuscript Accepted: 06-10-2024

Sportspersonship, Self-Efficacy and Sports Motivation of SOCCSKSARGEN Regional Athletic Association (SRAA) Athletes

Jestoni B. Boston*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study determined the domains of sportspersonship and self-efficacy that significantly influence the sport motivation as well as the lived experiences of the SRAA athletes in Region XII during the fourth quarter of 2023. The study was a mixed method using the convergent design among SRAA athletes selected through random sampling and participants for in-depth interview and focus-group discussion selected through purposive sampling. Mean and standard deviation, and linear regression were used for the statistical treatment of data. The results revealed that sportspersonship, self-efficacy, and sports motivation are high. Moreover, athlete self-efficacy influences sports motivation. On the other hand, the experiences of the athletes relative to sportspersonship and self-efficacy that shaped their beliefs, attitudes, and commitments include manifestation of relishing moments, constructive criticism, sportspersonship, performance optimization, and adherence to sports ethics, and positive mindset. Themes emerged on the roles of experiences in shaping the beliefs of the participants include self-belief, adaptability, and determination. The themes that emerged that shaped the attitudes of the participants include self-discipline, skill enhancement, and gratification. Meanwhile the experiences that shaped the commitment of the athletes include self-motivation for skills improvement and commitment to excellence in sports performance.

Keywords: *Physical Education, sportspersonship, self-efficacy, sports motivation*

Introduction

Sports motivation is the drive to take part and persist in an activity. Athletes are subjected to severe levels of competitiveness and pressure as a result of the high standards set for them. Globally, more than 35 percent of athletes have difficulty staying motivated to improve their performance because of the abovementioned factors (Saxon, 2023). Motivation is a topic that is often misunderstood in the world of sports. Having low or high motivation is not the same thing as being unmotivated. Before a competition begins, the comments of a coach or trainer may raise encouragement but may not boost motivation (White & Duda, 2021).

In the United States, more than 80 percent of the athletes have been impacted with poor motivation brought by many factors. Similarly, more than 50 percent of the American show poor motivation during sporting events. In Europe, motivation for sports activities is a complex phenomenon. The poor motivation among athletes has poor direction to achieving their goals by some needs, impulses, desires, and motives. The athletes with poor motivation experiences not performing tasks in their chosen sport activity. This has led to poor intensity and poor direction of their behavior towards sport and ultimately, they become unsuccessful in games when they attempt to perform a particular skill (Kondric et al., 2023). Only 12% of the athletes are seen with good motivation to perform better in sports. Athletes in the Philippines confront a wide range of challenges, including low self-esteem and distraction from the game as a consequence of high expectations placed on them. An athlete's confidence and competence are hindered by this sort of test, making it difficult for them to do well in a tournament. Poor motivation among athletes is a direct effect of these challenges and issues.

A significant propensity to adopt sportspersonship like actions within competitive circumstances may result from a prevailing sensation of autonomy and enjoyment towards sport involvement. Better sportspersonship leads to better sports motivation among students and athletes. On the other hand, Rogowska et al. (2022) cited that favorable correlation between athlete self-efficacy and sportspersonship was mentioned. Self-efficacy influences one's degree of effort and motivation when confronted with challenging circumstances, as well as one's decision-making and goal-setting processes. Athletes with a strong sense of athlete self-efficacy are more likely to behave responsibly, persevere through difficult circumstances, and put out maximum effort in competition. Furthermore, Gaspari Nutrition (2023) argued that many athletes who are not motivated are not inclined to show up training sessions, and will not train hard. An athlete cannot expect to win if they do not push themselves, and so motivation becomes one of the main things that separate the winners from the losers. Also, Hatch et al. (2023) cited that the presence of poor sportspersonship significantly increases the likelihood that an athlete may be demotivated from competing in an event. This may have an impact on how competitive the game is and how the participants feel about their own play.

The reason for the researcher to conduct the study is the presence of many gaps. Sport Psychology (2024) cited that sports motivation is the mental process that initiates, sustains, or guides an athlete's behavior such as training, approach to competition, managing adversity, and performance. First, little is known about how local factors affecting the motivation of the athletes in sports. Motivation is the driving force behind the athlete. A motivated athlete gets out of bed each morning and puts in the effort during training session and during competition. A motivated athlete is more likely to succeed in their chosen sport than an unmotivated athlete. Also, Jensen (2023) cited that unsportsmanlike conduct on the field or court can have far-reaching effects on team members. It disrupts the harmony of the team, erodes trust among players, and can be a catalyst for division. Similarly, Lochbaum et al. (2023) cited those athletes with

poor self-efficacy and sportspersonship lead to poor sports motivation. Athletes with poor self-efficacy are likely not being able to set goals, do not persist in the face of setbacks, or perform poorer under pressure (Lochbaum et al., 2023). Athletes have been reported to have elevated levels of mental toughness, as measured by measures of confidence and motivation. Motivation is less evident and athletes do not have the willpower to get up and be active. Moreover, the lack of motivation affects their performance. In the study of Vallerand and Losier (2023), a good sports motivation allows better sportspersonship among athletes. Similarly, Rogowska et al. (2022) cited that better athlete self-efficacy led to better sportspersonship.

Motivation is difficult to measure as researchers have conducted very few studies on the subject among athletes. Furthermore, most of the studies involve qualitative and quantitative in nature. Hence, the conduct of studies relating to sportspersonship, athlete self-efficacy, and sports motivation can be potentially useful to future researchers as part of the aforementioned literature and studies, they may also contribute to the body of information on the aforementioned factors and their issues in general. The findings of this research may be more credible if they are widely disseminated and published on local, national, and worldwide platforms, presented at public forums, and published in journals.

Methodology

Research Design

The convergent design under mix method approach. The convergent design is a one-phase design where both quantitative and qualitative data collected and analyzed, then compared the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data to see if the data confirms or disconfirms each other (Gonzaga University, 2024). On the other hand, mix method combines quantitative and qualitative methods may reveal more nuance than either alone. This is because combining methods compensates for the limitations of employing each one on its own (Voxco, 2023) and helps the researcher to acquire a more complete picture of the topic at hand. When it comes to synthesizing and interpreting qualitative and quantitative information, the convergent design is characterized by progressive, consecutive, and continual revisions (Hong et al., 2017). When conducting the quantitative portion of the study, the researcher will choose a descriptive-correlational strategy in which the focus is on identifying correlations between variables rather than establishing a causal link (Quaranta, 2017).

In the quantitative phase, the researcher used descriptive-correlational design. Quantitative research means collecting and analyzing numerical data to describe characteristics, find correlations, or test hypotheses (Allen, 2017). On one hand, the descriptive research tries to collect data methodically so as to provide a complete picture of whatever it is being studied, whether it a phenomenon, a scenario, or a population. In particular, it aids in responding to the when, where, how, and what rather than the why of the research challenge (Voxco, 2021). Questions on sportspersonship, self-efficacy, and motivation will be addressed in the research. On the other hand, the correlational design will determine whether significant relationships exist between variables. In a correlational study, the researcher does not actively intervene in any of the variables under question. The magnitude and/or direction of an association between two or more variables is represented by their correlation. Positive and negative correlations are equally possible (Bhandari, 2022). The study's goal is to establish a connection between motivation, sportspersonship, and confidence in one's own abilities. In the quantitative phase, the researcher should use a descriptive-correlational design because she wants to characterize the connection between sports motivation and the following: sportspersonship and self-efficacy of the players. We used a modified version of a five-point Likert scale survey to conduct our research.

In the qualitative phase, the researcher used a phenomenological approach. To do phenomenological research, one must suspend any preconceived notions about the event or thing being studied. To put it another way, phenomenological research designs are used to determine the universality of a phenomena by examining the perspectives of people who have experienced it (Groenewald, 2014).

Overall, the use of the mixed method design enables researchers to conceptually and analytically integrate quantitative and qualitative data with traditional epidemiological and quantitative methods of research to facilitate translation. Mixed methods are less tied to disciplines and established research paradigms. They offer more flexibility in designing this study, allowing the researcher to combine aspects of different types of studies to distill the most informative results. Also, mixed methods research can also combine theory generation and hypothesis testing within a single study, which is unusual for standalone qualitative or quantitative studies.

Participants

The methods of selection of participants in the quantitative and qualitative strands are described below.

Quantitative Strand

There are 323 athletes that were selected for the study. Random sampling technique was used to give every athlete the chance to be selected.

To participate in the research, the respondent must be an SRAA athlete for at least one (1) year and have participated in any competition in the local, regional, or national level. Additionally, the athlete must sign the Certificate of Consent Form and the Assent Form. On the other hand, athletes who have not competed in SRAA MEET in the last two years were excluded from the study.

Qualitative Strand

Purposive sampling was used to choose nine (9) participants for the in-depth interview (IDI) and nine (9) participants for the focus-group discussion (FGD). The participants were chosen through a purposive sampling design, a non-probability sampling method in which researchers use their own discretion in selecting survey respondents from the public at large (Alchemer, 2021). Consequently, the selection of the participants for the IDI and FGD met the same criteria in the selection of the respondents for the study.

To participate in the research, the respondent must be an SRAA athlete for at least one (1) year and have participated in any competition in the local, regional, or national level. Additionally, the athlete must sign the Certificate of Consent Form and the Assent Form. On the other hand, athletes who have not competed in SRAA MEET in the last two years were excluded from the study.

Quantitative Strand

The research used three customized instruments. Measures of sportspersonship in Part 1 was derived from Vallerand et al.'s (1997) "The Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Scale (MSOS-25)," which includes indicators like "respect for social conventions," "respect for the rules and the officials," "respect and concern for the opponent," and "negative approach toward the practice of sport." According to Knortz's (2009) research, the reliability index for the questionnaire is 0.74. The ranges for each parameter are shown below.

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Sportspersonship among the athletes is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Sportspersonship among the athletes is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Sportspersonship among the athletes is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Sportspersonship among the athletes is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Sportspersonship among the athletes is never manifested.

Athlete self-efficacy was assessed in Section 2 using a scale with four subscales (professional thinking efficacy, personality efficacy, sport discipline efficacy, and psychological) developed by Koçak (2020). The questionnaire is very consistent, with a reliability rating of 0.88. The bounds for each parameter are detailed below.

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The self-efficacy of the athletes is always demonstrated.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The self-efficacy of the athletes is oftentimes demonstrated.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The self-efficacy of the athletes is sometimes demonstrated.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The self-efficacy of the athletes is rarely demonstrated.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The self-efficacy of the athletes is never demonstrated.

Based on research by Pelletier et al. (1995), "The Sport Motivation Scale (SMS-28)" examines athletes' motivation in the following areas: There are many types of motivation: intrinsic (the desire to learn and grow), extrinsic (the need for recognition and praise), extrinsic (the desire for control from others), and amotivation. Clancy et al. (2017) found that the questionnaire's alpha value was more than 0.8, indicating its good reliability. The bounds for each parameter are detailed below.

Range of Means	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	The sport motivation of the athletes is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	High	The sport motivation of the athletes is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The sport motivation of the athletes is sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	The sport motivation of the athletes is rarely evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	The sport motivation of the athletes is never evident.

Qualitative Strand

The study included individual interviews and focus groups with SRAA players. For the IDI and FGD, the researcher utilized a validated open-ended questionnaire to inquire participants on the significance of the quantitative results.

Data Analysis

For the quantitative strand, the athletes' replies to questions on sportspersonship, self-efficacy, and sport motivation were averaged to provide a mean, and the standard deviation revealed any variability or variance in the data. However, the Pearson-r showed how closely the variables are related to one another. The research analyzed how sportspersonship and self-efficacy correlate with sports motivation. Finally, the predictive domains of independent variables were identified using linear regression. The study's goal was to identify the aspects of sportspersonship and self-efficacy that have the greatest impact on players' dedication to their sports. Meanwhile, on the qualitative strand, Colaizzi's method of data treatment was used in this part of the investigation. According to Morrow et al. (2015), Colaizzi's unique seven-step approach offers a thorough analysis since each stage is performed in close proximity to the data. The final product is a participant-validated, succinct but comprehensive explanation of the phenomena under research. The success of the approach relies on the collection of detailed descriptions of real-life events from real people. These stories may be gathered in a variety of forms, including in-person interviews, written narratives, blogs, research diaries, internet interviews, and so on.

Trustworthiness of the Study

In order to ascertain the trustworthiness of the study, the researcher adhered to the four suggested criteria for evaluating interpretive research conducted by Lincoln and Guba (1985). These criteria include credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. The trustworthiness of this study was ensured by conducting a comprehensive data collection process using surveys, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions for triangulation.

Results and Discussion

Quantitative Results

Status of Sportspersonship of the SRAA Athletes

The status of the sportspersonship of the SRAA athletes as assessed by the students as reflected in Table 1.1 has an overall mean of 3.42, described as high, which means that sportspersonship among the athletes is frequently manifested. In addition, a standard deviation of 0.31 indicates that the students' responses are basically the same.

Table 1.1. *Status of Sportspersonship of the SRAA Athletes*

	Mean	SD	Description
Respect for Social Conventions	4.39	.62	Very High
Respect for Rules and Officials	3.33	.40	Moderate
Respect for One's Full Commitment	3.80	.47	High
Respect and Concern for the Opponent	3.92	.79	High
Negative Approach toward the Practice of Sport	1.68	.53	Very Low
Overall Mean	3.42	.31	High

Status of Athlete Self-Efficacy of SRAA Athletes

The status of the athlete self-efficacy of the SRAA athletes as assessed by the students as reflected in Table 1.2 has an overall mean of 4.18, described as high, which means that self-efficacy of the athletes is frequently demonstrated. In addition, a standard deviation of 0.41 indicates that the students' responses are the same.

Table 1.2. *Status of Athlete Self-Efficacy of SRAA Athletes*

	Mean	SD	Description
Professional Thought Efficacy	3.70	.68	High
Personality Efficacy	4.29	.59	Very High
Sport Discipline Efficacy	4.20	0.93	Very High
Psychological Efficacy	4.54	.57	Very High
Overall Mean	4.18	.41	High

Status of Sports Motivation of SRAA Athletes

The status of the sports motivation of the SRAA athletes as assessed by the students as reflected in Table 1.3 has an overall mean of 3.99, described as high, which means that status of sports motivation of the athletes is frequently evident. In addition, a standard deviation of 0.41 indicates that the students' responses are the same.

Table 1.3. *Status of Sports Motivation of SRAA Athletes*

	Mean	SD	Description
Intrinsic Motivation – To Know	4.45	.56	Very High
Intrinsic Motivation – To Accomplish	4.34	.61	Very High
Intrinsic Motivation- To Experience Stimulation	4.38	.62	Very High
Extrinsic Motivation – Identified	4.43	.58	Very High
Extrinsic Motivation – Introjected	4.11	.74	High
Extrinsic Motivation – External Regulation	4.09	.72	High
Amotivation	2.13	.99	Low
Overall Mean	3.99	.41	High

Influence of Sportspersonship and Athlete Efficacy on Sport Motivation

Table 2 shows the results of the multiple regression analysis. It reveals that athlete self-efficacy is a significant predictor of sport motivation with a p-value that is less than .05 level of significance (2-tailed) ($F=86.351$, $p < .05$) with a positive standardized beta of .569. Hence, it suggested that for every unit increase in the value of the athlete self-efficacy, there is a corresponding increase of .569 in the level of sport motivation. Notably, the results show that in singular capacity, the sportspersonship does not significantly influence sport motivation with a p-value greater than .05 ($p > .05$) with a combined standardized beta of .048. Evidently, between the two independent variables in the study, athlete self-efficacy recorded as the only influence on the sport motivation of the SRAA athletes.

Table 2. *Influence of Sportspersonship and Athlete Self-efficacy on Sport Motivation*

<i>Sport Motivation</i>				
<i>Individual Influence of Predictors</i>	<i>Standardized Coefficient</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Sportspersonship	.048	.978	.329	Not Significant
Athlete Self-Efficacy	.569	11.489	.000	Significant
<i>Combined Influence of Predictors</i>				
R	.591			
R ²	.346			
F	86.351			
p	.000			Significant

Meanwhile, the model explains 34.6 percent of the variance of the sport motivation of the SRAA students having athlete self-efficacy as the only predictor as indicated by $r^2=.346$. This means that 65.4 percent of the variance of sport motivation of the SRAA students can be attributed to other factors from the variables explored in the study.

Qualitative Results

Profile of the Participants

Table 3 shows the profile of the participants in the qualitative strand of the study. As reflected in the table below, the total number of participants in the qualitative strand is 18 students. They were purposively selected by the researcher to gain further information for the qualitative strand of this mixed method study.

Table 3. *Profile of the Participants*

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Study Group</i>	<i>Divisions</i>	<i>Sports Event</i>
IDI #1	Male	IDI	General Santos City	Dance Sport (Latin)
IDI #2	Female	IDI	South Cotabato	Volleyball
IDI #3	Female	IDI	Koronadal	Badminton (Doubles)
IDI #4	Male	IDI	Koronadal	Badminton (Singles)
IDI #5	Male	IDI	Cotabato Province	Wrestling
IDI #6	Female	IDI	Cotabato Province	Lawn Tennis (Single)
IDI #7	Female	IDI	Cotabato Province	Taekwondo
IDI #8	Male	IDI	Kidapawan City	Volleyball
IDI #9	Female	IDI	Kidapawan City	Table Tennis (Single)
FGD #1	Male	FGD	General Santos City	Basketball
FGD #2	Female	FGD	South Cotabato	Softball
FGD #3	Male	FGD	Koronadal	Sepak Takraw
FGD #4	Female	FGD	Koronadal	Gymnastics
FGD #5	Female	FGD	Cotabato Province	Futsal
FGD #6	Male	FGD	Cotabato Province	Athletics (Discus Throw)
FGD #7	Female	FGD	Cotabato Province	Chess
FGD #8	Male	FGD	Kidapawan City	Basketball
FGD #9	Male	FGD	Kidapawan City	Football

Further, as indicated in the table, there were nine participants selected for the IDI and another nine participants for the FGD. There was an equal distribution of male and female athletes. Furthermore, the participants were mostly from Cotabato Province and Koronadal. Lastly, the participants were into different events such as badminton, volleyball, basketball, and other events.

Lived Experiences of Participants Concerning Sports Motivation

Table 4 shows the lived experiences of the students concerning sports motivation. The data gathered through IDI and FGD were transcribed, coded, grouped, and organized into themes. In this particular research question on the lived experiences of the students concerning sports motivation, six themes were created and these are: manifestation of relishing moments, constructive criticism, sportspersonship, performance optimization, adherence to sports ethics, and positive mindset.

Table 4. *Lived Experiences of Participants as Regards in Sports Motivation*

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Manifestation of Relishing Moments	Enjoying the company of my teammates
	Having a coach who enjoys and have fun during the game
	Feeling excited when the team earns a point
Constructive Criticism	Knowing my mistakes help me improve my skills
	Pointing out my mistakes contributes to becoming a better athlete
	Realizing my mistakes and follow the advice of my coach
	Accepting criticism and feedback

Themes	Core Ideas
Sportspersonship	Feeling grateful since my coach wants the best in me Complimenting and showing respect to opponents after the game Praising and congratulating them after the game Giving positive comments to the opponent like “Nice Game”. recognizing skills and effort of the opponent Giving my best during the game
Performance Optimization	Believing in myself that I can do it and focusing on my goals Creating a game plan to achieve goals Using of multiple strategies during the game Setting of achievable and realistic goals Listening carefully and obeying rules and regulations of the game Paying attention and be open minded to every part of the game
Adherence to Sports Ethics	Knowing consequences of not following the rules and guidelines Respecting decision of the referee Learning basic, foundational, and advance skills of the game Observing strengths and weaknesses of the opponent to identify counter attacks
Positive mindset	Mastering proper technique in playing the game Performing positive self-talk and visualizing success Having a strong belief to what I can do and show.

Manifestation of Relishing Moments. When the students were interviewed about their lived experiences on sports motivation, the following themes emerged: enjoying the company of my teammates, having a coach who enjoys and have fun during the game, and feeling excited when the team earns a point. Participants have shared that:

Enjoy the game and always think positive.

Many enjoyments I received from my coach but then there were points with sadness but then I tried to think that it will help me to grow as a player.

Practice makes perfect as I said so like by practicing, we players could enjoy.

Constructive Criticism. When students were interviewed about their experiences on sports motivation, the following themes emerged: knowing their mistakes help them improve my skills, pointing out their mistakes that contribute to becoming a better athlete, realizing their mistakes and following the advice of their coach, accepting criticism and feedback, and feeling grateful since my coach wants the best in me. Participants shared that:

It's okay to make mistake sometimes and because it is inevitable, especially in sports. At the same time, I always try to be better each game.

So, the improvements in my life as an athlete is that attributes to sports motivation is that I learned from my mistakes before and it helps my me to grow and to have a good performance right now.

It is embarrassing at first but you should accept criticisms and feedback and use them to become better in the future.

My coach is strict and points out my mistakes in order for me to become better.

One of the achievements is when my coach is able to point out my mistakes so that I will improve with my sport.

Mistakes are meant to be corrected. So, at first, I feel disappointment to myself because I can't do the task correctly but then above all I realize that it is vital for us to correct those mistakes.

Sportspersonship. When the students were interviewed about their lived experiences on sports motivation, the following themes emerged: complimenting and showing respect to opponents after the game, praising and congratulating them after the game, giving positive comments to the opponent, and recognizing skills and effort of the opponent. Participants shared that:

After the game, when I see my opponents, I congratulate and give them compliments for their good performance.

I congratulated my opponents for winning the game like for example, shaking hands with them and saying that they did their best and they did it well to win the game and they really appreciated that a lot when you compliment...

Just simply congratulating them and praising how good they are during the competition for their skills and effort.

I would always congratulate my opponents regardless of the outcome. It's not just about winning or losing. It's about acknowledging the effort and dedication and hard work of each participant has contributed to...

Performance Optimization. When the participants were interviewed about their lived experiences on sports motivation, the following themes emerged: giving their best during the game, believing in themselves that they can do it and focusing on their goals, creating a game plan to achieve goals, using of multiple strategies during the game, and setting of achievable and realistic goals. Participants shared that:

I try to give my best in the game.

As a softball player, one of the ways to achieve optimum performance goal is to be serious with the sport through communication and teamwork.

I always have my strategy in games and I think as to how the game works.

My ways to achieve the winning or the title, I have the strategy of knowing the capability of my opponent because I believe that by that I can learn something that can strike or can counter their attack for me.

To achieve performance goal in competition, individual often employed a combination of strategies planning; focus training, mental preparation and maintaining a discipline lifestyle.

Setting realistic and achievable goals allows me to experience success and build confidence.

Adherence to Sports Ethics. When the students were interviewed about their lived experiences on sports motivation, the following themes emerged: listening carefully and obeying rules and regulations of the game, participating and cooperating conscientiously, paying attention and be open minded to every part of the game, knowing consequences of not following the rules and guidelines, respecting decision of the referee, learning basic, foundational, and advance skills of the game, and observing strengths and weaknesses of the opponent to identify counterattacks. The participants shared:

Follow and obey the rules and regulations of the game in order not to be disqualified.

I think by participating and cooperating in one team is showing that you are respecting the rules of the sport.

I obey the rules by familiarizing them and always thinking of the consequences if you are not obeying the rules.

Adhering to the rules of the sport, respecting the decision of the referee and the following guidelines set by the team are essentially component of a good sportsmanship.

So, the technical skills that I have a learn is tutorial on how to be a better athlete.

...I take risks in the game and conquer my fears to attack. I have to be observant with the opponent's weakness and strength.

Positive Mindset. When the students were interviewed on their lived experiences on sports motivation, the following themes emerged: being motivated when friends and families are watching the game, praying and believing in themselves boost their confidence, performing positive self-talk and visualizing success, and having a strong belief to what they can do and show. Participants shared that:

I am motivated if my friends, family, and my girlfriend watch me during the game.

I boost my self confidence in sports by watching videos of my favorite athlete and inspiring myself by watching them.

Positive self-talk, visualize success, and focusing on task achievement can build a strong mental foundation for me.

Having a strong belief to what I can do and show.

Data Integration of the Salient Qualitative and Quantitative Findings

The data in Table 5 are the joint display of the salient qualitative and quantitative findings on sportspersonship and self-efficacy on the acquisition of sports motivation among SRAA athletes. The primary segment relates to the review's angles, trailed constantly and third sections where the quantitative and the subjective discoveries are uncovered. The fourth segment legitimizes the possibility of mix. The subjective and quantitative information were analyzed for likenesses and contrasts and coordinated into the outcomes. In the consolidating examination, the center is the idea of information reconciliation, which portrays the sets of quantitative and subjective discoveries that are combined.

Table 5. Joint Display of the Salient Qualitative and Quantitative Findings

Aspect or Focal Point	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature of Integration
Sportspersonship	Table 1.1 on status of sportspersonship of athletes under indicator, Respect for social conventions on item 1 congratulating opponents is rated very high, M=4.50, SD=.82 and item 5 shake	Table 4.1 on lived experiences, has a theme <i>sportspersonship</i> include core ideas, which illustrates that athlete's compliment and show respect to opponent, praising and congratulating them after the game and	Merging-Converging

Aspect or Focal Point	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature of Integration
	hands with the opponents after the game is rated Very High, M=4.49, SD=.91	giving positive comments regarding the game like “Nice Game”.	
	Table 1.1 on status of sportspersonship of athletes under indicator Respect for rules and Officials on item 1 obey the referee is rated Very High, M=4.48, SD=.96 and item 2 respect the rules is rated very high, M=4.69, SD=.74	Table 4.2 on lived experiences, has a theme <i>adherence to sports ethics</i> contain core ideas highlighting listening carefully and obeying rules and respecting decision of the referee.	
	Table 1.1 on status of sportspersonship of athletes under the indicator Respect for one’s full commitment on item 2 don’t give up even after making mistakes is rated Very Low, M=1.29, SD=.53 and item 3 think ways to improve weaknesses is rated Very High, M=4.54, SD=.78	Table 4.1 on lived experiences has a theme <i>constructive criticism</i> with the core ideas knowing my mistakes help me improve my skills, accepting criticism and feedback and pointing my mistakes contribute to becoming a better athlete.	
Self-Efficacy	Table 1.2 on status on athlete self-efficacy under the indicator Professional thought Efficacy on item 1 work devotedly to achieve performance, is rated Very High, M=4.51, SD=.84	Table 5.2 on lived experiences, has a theme <i>performance optimization</i> with core ideas such as giving my best during the game, setting achievable and realistic goals and creating game plan to achieve goal.	Merging-Converging
	Table 1.2 on status on athlete self-efficacy under the indicator Personality Efficacy on item 1 cooperate and work in cohesion with my stakeholders, is rated Very High, M=4.34, SD=.84, item 2 high self-confidence is rated High, M=4.02, SD=.93	Table 5.2 on lived experiences has a theme <i>adherence to sports ethics</i> with core idea as participating and cooperating conscientiously. Moreover, <i>the positive mindset</i> with core idea praying and believing in myself boost my confidence.	
	Table 1.2 on status on athlete self-efficacy under the indicator Psychological Efficacy on item 2 I motivate myself is rated Very High, M=4.57, SD=.78	Table 4.1 on lived experiences has a theme <i>performance optimization</i> with core idea believing in myself that I can do it and ensuring mental preparation to perform better during the game and giving my best during the game.	
Sports Motivation	Table 3 on status of sports motivation of athletes under indicator, Intrinsic Motivation to accomplished, on item 1 I feel a lot of personal satisfaction while mastering certain difficult training techniques, is rated Very High, M=4.38, SD=.73	Table 4.1 on lived experiences, has a theme <i>Performance Optimization</i> with core ideas that include mastering proper technique in playing the game, learning basic, foundational and advance skills of the game and analyzing placement of the ball during the game	Merging-Converging
	Table 1.3 on status of sports motivation of athletes under indicator, Intrinsic motivation experience stimulation, on item 2, for the excitement I feel when I am really involved in the activity., is rated Very High, M=4.40 SD=.73	Table 4.1 on the lived experiences has a theme <i>Manifestation of Relishing Moments</i> with the core idea feeling excited when the team earns a point.	
Influence of Sportspersonship on Sport Motivation	The standardized coefficients and p-values indicates that sportspersonship has no significant influence on sports motivation with a p-value of .329.	Sportspersonship particularly on <i>constructive criticism</i> allows athlete to improve skills. Additionally, pointing	Merging-Diverging

Aspect or Focal Point	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature of Integration
Influence of Athlete Self-efficacy on Sport Motivation	The standardized coefficients and p-values indicates that athlete efficacy has a significant influence on sports motivation (p<.05)	mistakes contribute to their becoming a better athlete. Self-Efficacy influences sport motivation of athletes characterized by self-belief and positivity, resilience and adaptability and physical well-being. It allows athlete to maintain fairness during the game, recognizing teamwork as important, having a healthy lifestyle and engaging in regular training to enhance fitness level.	Merging-Converging

Merging-Converging. In particular, the findings for the nature of data integration in merging-converging consist of the following focal points. For the focal point of sportpersonship, under indicator respect for social conventions on item 1 indicating about congratulating opponents, obtained a mean rating of 4.50, which is described is very high and when merged to qualitative results, converged with the theme sportpersonship and fairness, trust, respect, balance, and equality. If it is done to form an agreement, the agreement is not official until the hands are parted.

For the focal point of self-efficacy under indicator professional thought efficacy on item 1 – work devotedly to achieve performance – having obtained a mean score of 4.51, which is very high, converged with the theme performance optimization and sports self-efficacy with core ideas such as giving my best during the game, setting achievable and realistic goals and creating game plan to achieve goal.

On the focal point athlete self-efficacy on sport motivation, the standardized coefficients and p-values indicates that athlete efficacy has a significant influence on sports motivation (p<.05). This converges with self-efficacy that influences sport motivation of athletes characterized by self-belief and positivity, resilience and adaptability and physical well-being. It allows athlete to maintain fairness during the game, recognizing teamwork as important, having a healthy lifestyle and engaging in regular training to enhance fitness level.

Merging-Diverging. On the other hand, the findings for the nature of data integration in merging-diverging consist the following focal points. On the focal point influence of sportpersonship on sports motivation, standardized coefficients and p-values indicates that sportpersonship has no significant influence on sports motivation with a p-value of .329. Sportpersonship particularly on constructive criticism and personal growth allows athlete to improve skills. Additionally, pointing mistakes contribute to their becoming a better athlete.

The status of sportpersonship of the athletes was high with description of oftentimes manifested. This implies going all out during practices, asking the referee to stop the game so that he or she can get help when an opponent gets hurt, and trying to rectify the situation if I see that the opponent is unjustly penalized. The discoveries are consistent with the cases of Chantal et al. (2016) that sportpersonship is the one's full responsibility for the game, the guidelines and authorities, social shows, and the rival as well as the overall shortfall of a pessimistic methodology toward support. The social mental methodology further recommends that recognizing three key components: sportpersonship conduct, sportpersonship directions, and the improvement of sportpersonship orientations is significant. Donahue et al. (2019) stated that athletes with a high orientation toward concern for the rules and officials would be less likely to cheat than athletes with a low orientation. Martin (2021) argued that sportpersonship builds character and teaches people different qualities they can use later in life.

The status of self-efficacy of the athletes was high with description of oftentimes manifested. Cakiroglu (2021) stated that self-efficacy in athletics is the confidence an athlete has in his or her own abilities to bring about a desired result in competition. Furthermore, the American Psychological Association (2022) cited that one's sense of self-efficacy reveals how confident they are in their abilities to influence their own drive, actions, and relationships. These mental assessments affect all aspect of a person's life, from the ambitions they pursue to the efforts they make to accomplish their objectives to the probability that they will succeed at a certain task. Self-efficacy beliefs, on the other hand, are expected to change across domains of functioning and contextual settings.

The status of sports motivation of the SRAA athletes was high with the description of oftentimes evident. Cohn (2023) cited that motivation prompts and maintains actions like training, competition strategy, dealing with setbacks, and ultimately, performance. Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation have a role in athletics yet they serve different purposes. Meanwhile, Cook (2019) argued that an athlete cannot overstate the importance of motivation when it comes to improving your performance in any sport, whether you are playing for fun or to win. It inspires athletes, motivates them to keep going, and reassures them that they can do anything.

Sportpersonship significantly influences athlete self-efficacy. The finding backs up Rogowska et al.'s (2022) assertion that self-efficacy and sports motivation are strongly linked. Individuals with high self-viability are roused to determine testing errands and do not show staying away from propensity, especially after disappointment, which can make sense of the relationship between self-adequacy and sports achievement. Increasing self-efficacy, on the other hand, is crucial to achieving high sports performance. Self-viability lessens pressure and gloomy feelings during challenges, controls what is happening, and oversees survival techniques to

support powerful execution, thus directs the connection between aggressive nervousness and inspiration and execution in sports. Decision-making and goal-setting, as well as one's level of effort and motivation in the face of a challenge, are all influenced by one's level of confidence in one's own abilities.

The findings and results of this study can provide additional information for athletes, physical education teachers, school administrators, sports leaders, sports program organizers, athletes, coaches, and sports enthusiasts. This study may serve as a reference for the lived experiences of the athletes concerning sports motivation as well as the roles of experiences shaping the beliefs, attitudes, and commitments of the participants to exhibit sports motivation. Universities in Mindanao and also around the Philippines can use the data to formulate, implement, and evaluate sports programs and policies.

The confirmation of the experiences of the SRAA athletes signifies different sports motivation and hence, the need to intensify sportsmanship and athlete self-efficacy to improve their sports motivation.

Conclusions

The status of sportpersonship of the SRAA athletes was rated high, which means described as oftentimes manifested. There was oftentimes manifestation of respect for social conventions, rules and officials, one's full commitment, opponent, and negative approach toward the practice of sport. Hence, the athletes uphold the spirit of competition, even when not required by the rules, as the core of sportpersonship. On one hand, the status of self-efficacy of the SRAA athletes was also rated high, which is oftentimes demonstrated. This implies oftentimes demonstration of professional thought efficacy, personality efficacy, sport discipline efficacy and psychological efficacy. Hence, the athletes have shown confidence in their ability to take the actions that would lead them to the desired outcomes in terms of performance. On the other hand, the status of sports motivation of the SRAA athletes was rated high, which is oftentimes evident. This is oftentimes evident on the following: intrinsic motivation – to know, intrinsic motivation – to accomplish, intrinsic motivation – to experience stimulation, extrinsic motivation – identified, extrinsic motivation – introjected, extrinsic motivation – external regulation, and amotivation. Hence, the athletes prompt and maintain actions like training, competition strategy, dealing with setbacks and ultimately, performance.

Between the two variables which is sportpersonship and self-efficacy – only athlete self-efficacy significantly influences sports motivation among SRAA athletes.

Six essential themes emerged from the lived experiences of the participants: manifestation of relishing moments, constructive criticism, sportpersonship, performance optimization, adherence to sports ethics, and positive mindset

The role of experiences shaping the belief of the participants have merged the themes such as self-belief, adaptability, and determination. While in shaping the attitude the following themes extracted included the self-discipline, skill enhancement, and gratification. And lastly, on the role of experiences that shaped in the commitment of sports motivation involved the themes such as self-motivation for skills improvement and commitment to excellence in sports performance

In the joint display of salient of quantitative and qualitative of the nature of the data integration showed a merging-converging and merging-diverging.

References

- Alchemer (2021). Purposive Sampling 101. Retrieved from <https://www.alchemer.com/resources/blog/purposive-sampling-101/>
- Allen, M. (2017). *The SAGE encyclopedia of communication research methods* (Vols. 1-4). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc doi: 10.4135/9781483381411
- Bhandari, P. (2022). Correlational Research. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/correlational-research>
- Cakiroglu, T. (2021). The Role of Athletic Self-efficacy and Athletic Perfectionism in Predicting Athletic Performance of Gazi University Student Athletes. *Journal of Educational Issues*, 7(2):2377-2263. doi: 10.5296/jei.v7i2.19108
- Clancy, R., Herring, M., and Campbell, M. (2017). Motivation Measures in Sport: A Critical Review and Bibliometric Analysis. *Front. Psychol.*, 09 March 2017 Sec. Quantitative Psychology and Measurement, 8. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00348
- Cohn, P. (2023). Sports Psychology: Letting Go of Errors. Retrieved from <https://www.peaksports.com/sports-psychology-blog/sports-psychology-letting-go-of-errors/>
- Cook, N. (2019). Benefits of Motivation on Sports Performance. Retrieved from <https://www.nataliecook.com/blog/benefits-of-motivation-on-sports-performance>
- Donahue, E., Miquelon, P., Valois, P., Goulet, C., Buist, A., & Vallerand, R. J. (2019). A motivational model of performance-enhancing substance use in elite athletes. *Journal of Sport & Exercise Psychology*, 28:502–511.
- Gaspari Nutrition (2023). How does motivation affect sports performance? Retrieved from <https://gasparinutrition.com/blogs/fitness-facts/how-does-motivation-affect-sports-performance>

- Gonzaga University (2024). Mixed Methods Research. Retrieved from <https://researchguides.gonzaga.edu/qualitative/mixed-methods>
- Groenewald, T. (2014). A phenomenological research design illustrated. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*.
- Hatch, S., Thomsen, D., and Waldron, J. (2023). Extrinsic rewards and motivation. Retrieved from <https://appliedsportpsych.org/resources/resources-for-coaches/extrinsic-rewards-and-motivation/>
- Hong, Q. N., Pluye, P., Bujold, M., and Wassef, M. (2017). Convergent and sequential synthesis designs: implications for conducting and reporting systematic reviews of qualitative and quantitative evidence. *Systematic Reviews*, 6(61). doi: 10.1186/s13643-017-0454-2
- Jensen, H. (2023). What are the effects of unsportsmanlike conduct to team members? Retrieved from <https://www.quora.com/What-are-the-effects-of-unsportsmanlike-conduct-to-team-members>
- Khaushik, V., and Walsh, C. (2019). Pragmatism as a Research Paradigm and Its Implications. Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0760/8/9/255>
- Knortz, G. (2009). A Case Study: Assessing the Validity and Reliability of the Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Scale Among College Athletes. Graduate Thesis: University of Vermont.
- Kondric, M., Sindik, J., Furjan-Mandic, G., and Schiefler, B. (2023). Participation Motivation and Student's Physical Activity among Sport Students in Three Countries. *J Sports Sci Med*. 2013 Mar; 12(1): 10–18.
- Lochbaum, M., Sisneros, C., Cooper, S., and Terry, P. (2023). Pre-Event Self-Efficacy and Sports Performance: A Systematic Review with Meta-Analysis. *Sports (Basel)*. 2023 Nov; 11(11): 222. doi: 10.3390/sports11110222
- Martin, J. (2021). The Importance of Sportspersonship. Retrieved from <https://www.ipl.org/essay/The-Importance-Of-Sportspersonship-In-High-School-P3UZGL2FJE8Rx>
- Morrow, R., Rodriguez, A., and King, N. (2015). Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological method. Retrieved from <https://eprints.hud.ac.uk/id/eprint/26984/1/>
- Pelletier, L. G., Fortier, M., Vallerand, R. J., Briere, N. M., Tuson, K. M., and Blais, M. R. (1995). Sports Motivation Scale (SMS-28). *Journal of Sports & Exercise Psychology*, 17:35-53.
- Rogowska, A., Tataruch, R., Niedzwiecki, K., and Wojciechowska-Maszkowska, B. (2022). The Mediating Role of Self-Efficacy in the Relationship between Approach Motivational System and Sports Success among Elite Speed Skating Athletes and Physical Education Students. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022 Mar; 19(5): 2899. doi: 10.3390/ijerph19052899
- Saxon, E. (2023). Athletes and their Mental and Physical Struggles. Retrieved from <https://stmuscolars.org/athletes-and-their-mental-and-physical-struggles>
- Sport Psychology (2024). What's the best motivation for athletes? Retrieved from <https://www.peaksports.com/sports-psychology-blog/whats-the-best-motivation-for-athletes/>
- Vallerand, R. J., Briere, N. M., Blanchard, C. M., and Provencher, J. (1997). The Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Scales (MSOS-25): Development and Validation of the Multidimensional Sportspersonship Orientation Scale. *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 19:197-206.
- Vallerand, R. J., Deshaies, P., Cuerrier, J.-P., Brière, N. M., & Pelletier, L. G. (1996). Toward a multidimensional definition of sportspersonship. *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 8:89–101. doi: 10.1080/10413209608406310
- Voxco (2021). Descriptive Research Design. Retrieved from <https://www.voxco.com/blog/descriptive-research-designx>
- Voxco (2023). What is Mixed Methods Research? Retrieved from <https://www.voxco.com/blog/mixed-methods-research/>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jestoni B. Boston

University of the Immaculate Conception – Philippines